

NDAC/LO/014

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WP2100: Attitude Reconstitution and SMS Update (Definition)

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1. Principles

The attitude reconstitution (AR) shall provide an a posteriori attitude ephemeris $\alpha_z(t)$, $\delta_z(t)$, $\omega(t)$ with an accuracy of the order of 0.15 as in all three axes. To this purpose it will use the quasi-continuous gyro signals, the star mapper transit times, IDT signal parameters, and star positions from the Input Catalogue (IC) or an updated version of it. We propose that the AR uses cubic splines to represent the attitude angles and that the Square-Root Information Smoother is used to estimate the spline coefficients. The mathematical details of this procedure are given in NDAC/LO/006.

The AR is carried out in two passes. In the first pass (AR1) only gyro and SM data are incorporated; this gives a preliminary attitude by means of which the IDT preprocessing is performed. The resulting IDT signal phases ($\hat{\beta}_3$) are incorporated in the second pass (AR2) in order to improve the spin attitude (about the z axis). The second pass also provides transit residuals for all programme stars observed with the SM.

The star-mapper stars update (SMSU) uses transit residuals from AR2 in order to improve current catalogue positions of programme stars. Previously (Location Estimator Definition, NDAC/LO/010, p. 9) it was envisaged to have an optional SMSU on the Danish side to help eliminating slit ambiguities. Since then, two important facts have become evident:

- that the set solutions do not need improved positions, but rather improved spin attitude in order to cope with slit errors (Petersen, 1982 Nov 16); and
- that the IC is almost accurate enough for the on-ground AR (NDAC/LO/013) and that therefore the quickest possible

updating of catalogue positions will minimize (and possibly eliminate) the amount of AR to be iterated.

The natural conclusion is that the SMSU should be performed on the English side, more or less in parallel with the AR, so that the latter always can benefit from the best current position estimates. This will also eliminate the transportation of transit residuals to Denmark and catalogue updates back to England. Hence the revised process diagram (p.

It follows that the reductions on the two sides normally use different catalogue versions. To avoid confusion it is essential that all data transferred between them are absolute, i.e. independent of catalogue positions to first order. This is already ensured for the main data streams, viz. attitude angles and grid coordinates. Needless to say, the original version (IC) must be retained independent of all updates.

2. Summary of I/O Data

The relevant Data Interface Descriptions (DID's) are:

DID#	SOURCE	DATA INPUT TO AR
22	SM Preprocessing	• transit times
23	SM Calibration	• SM reference line equations
24	Gyro Data	• gyro samples
25	RT Attitude	• Real-Time attitude angles
26	Star Catalogue	• astrometric data
27	Ephemerides	• barycentric motion of observer
28	IDT Signal Catalogue	• signal parameters and covariances (input to AR2)
29	AR1	• intermediary results ($\hat{\phi}_j^{-1}$, $\underline{G}_j$, $\underline{A}_j$, $\underline{z}_j$) (input to AR2)

DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM AR
2	Set Solution	• attitude angles (output from AR2)
12	IDT Pre-processing	• attitude angles (output from AR1)
30	SMS Update	• SM transit residuals (from AR2)

DID#	SOURCE	DATA INPUT TO SMS UPDATE
30	AR2	• SM transit residuals
31	Star Catalogue	• current position estimate and m.e.

DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM SMS UPDATE
32	Star Catalogue	• updated position estimate and m.e.

3. Method and Basic Equations

3.1. Attitude Reconstitution (AR1 and AR2)

Most of this has been detailed in NDAC/LO/006 and is not repeated here. A remark must be made however on the mean error of the SM observation equation (006.44). As mentioned on p. 13 of that note, it is a combination of the timing m.e. (σ_t) and the catalogue positional m.e. (σ_p). The latter should of course be in the "effective scanning direction" normal to the slits. This may be an important distinction with a partially updated catalogue where the accuracy may be quite anisotropic, and requires some elaboration. The right-hand side of the observation equation is

$$u_{\text{obs}} - u_{\text{comp}} = \eta_{fg}(\zeta_{\text{comp}}) - \eta_{\text{comp}} \quad (1)$$

where $u := \eta - \eta_{fg}(\zeta)$ as introduced in NDAC/LO/011 and $u_{\text{obs}} = 0$ by definition (at the observed transit time). Differencing we get

$$\Delta u = -\Delta\eta + \eta_{fg}^{\sim}(\zeta) \Delta\zeta \quad (2)$$

Introducing the angle q such that $-q$ is the position angle of the great circle arc from the star to z , we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta\eta \cos \zeta &= \cos q (\Delta\alpha \cos \delta) + \sin q (\Delta\delta) \\ \Delta\zeta &= -\sin q (\Delta\alpha \cos \delta) + \cos q (\Delta\delta) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

with

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \cos \zeta \cos q &= \cos \delta \sin \delta_z - \sin \delta \cos \delta_z \cos(\alpha - \alpha_z) \\ \cos \zeta \sin q &= \cos \delta_z \sin(\alpha - \alpha_z) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

(α, δ) being the position of the star. Defining the reference line inclination $i_{fg}(\zeta)$ by means of

$$\tan i_{fg}(\zeta) = \eta_{fg}^{\sim}(\zeta) \cos \zeta \quad (5)$$

we have from (2) and (3):

$$\Delta u \cos \zeta \cos i_{fg} = -\cos(q - i_{fg}) \Delta\alpha \cos \delta - \sin(q - i_{fg}) \Delta\delta \quad (6)$$

If $\underline{C}$ is the catalogue position covariance, $\text{Cov}(\Delta\alpha \cos \delta, \Delta\delta)'$, we get the total variance of the SM transit

$$\sigma_u^2 = (\dot{u}\sigma_\tau)^2 + (\cos \zeta \cos i_{fg})^{-2} \underline{a}' \underline{C} \underline{a} \quad (7)$$

$$\underline{a} = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos(q - i_{fg}) \\ -\sin(q - i_{fg}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

It is seen that the formula $\sigma_p^2 + \Omega^2 \sigma_\tau^2$ given in NDAC/LO/006 is in fact wrong, since $\sigma_p = \sqrt{\underline{a}' \underline{C} \underline{a}}$ is to be multiplied by $\sec i_{fg}$ as in (7).

3.2. Star Mapper Stars Update (SMSU)

This should aim at improving, within a period of the order of a week from the corresponding AR, the positions of the programme stars used in the AR. To operate a continually changing star catalogue is obviously a delicate business, and a discussion is warranted on the data-handling aspects of it.

We proceed from the assumption that the star catalogue shall only contain the original (IC = Input Catalogue) astrometric parameters and the latest update (CC = Current Catalogue), so as not to become unwieldy after several updatings; yet it must be possible to correct erroneous updatings and there must never be confusion about which version differential data refer to.

For each programme star, there is first the IC astrometric parameters $\bar{\alpha}_0, \bar{\delta}_0, \bar{\mu}_\alpha, \bar{\mu}_\delta, \bar{\Pi}$, which must not be changed. The barycentric coordinates at mid-epoch (α_0, δ_0) refer to $t_0 \equiv \text{TEPOCH} \approx 1988.5$. The current position (i.e. the current best estimate of the true α_0, δ_0) is given by the difference vector

$$\underline{d} = \begin{pmatrix} (\alpha_0 - \bar{\alpha}_0) \cos \bar{\delta}_0 \\ \delta_0 - \bar{\delta}_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

with covariance $\underline{C} = \text{Cov}(\underline{d})$. We may distinguish the various updated estimates by a subscript k ,

$$(\underline{C}_k, \underline{d}_k), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (10)$$

although they are in reality successively overwritten in the catalogue. In particular, $\underline{d}_0 = \underline{0}$ for the initial data (IC), with $\underline{C}_0$ containing the IC position variances.

New information can always be cast in the form of normalized observation equations

$$\underline{D}\underline{d} + \underline{v} = \underline{f} \quad (11)$$

where $\underline{v}$ is the observation noise vector with $E(\underline{v}) = \underline{0}$, $E(\underline{v}\underline{v}') = \underline{I}$. Using conventional least-squares, we get the updating equations

$$\underline{C}_{k+1} = (\underline{C}_k^{-1} + \underline{D}'\underline{D})^{-1}, \quad \underline{d}_{k+1} = \underline{C}_{k+1} (\underline{C}_k^{-1} \underline{d}_k + \underline{D}'\underline{f}) \quad (12)$$

As an alternative to the state-covariance formalism $(\underline{C}, \underline{d})$, one may prefer the information array $(\underline{H}, \underline{h})$ defined by

$$\underline{H} = \underline{C}^{-1}, \quad \underline{h} = \underline{C}^{-1} \underline{d}$$

and which gives the simpler updating equations corresponding to the accumulation of normals,

$$\underline{H}_{k+1} = \underline{H}_k + \underline{D}'\underline{D}, \quad \underline{h}_{k+1} = \underline{h}_k + \underline{D}'\underline{f} \quad (13)$$

It is evident that (13), and therefore also (12), is a reversible process. That is, the updating (12) or (13) can be undone any time later by performing the "downdating"

$$\underline{H}_{k+1} = \underline{H}_k - \underline{D}'\underline{D}, \quad \underline{h}_{k+1} = \underline{h}_k - \underline{D}'\underline{f} \quad (14)$$

or

$$\underline{C}_{k+1} = (\underline{C}_k^{-1} - \underline{D}'\underline{D})^{-1}, \quad \underline{d}_{k+1} = \underline{C}_{k+1} (\underline{C}_k^{-1} \underline{d}_k - \underline{D}'\underline{f}) \quad (15)$$

assuming of course that $(\underline{D}, \underline{f})$ or $(\underline{D}'\underline{D}, \underline{D}'\underline{f})$ has been saved. [The form $(\underline{D}'\underline{D}, \underline{D}'\underline{f})$ is obviously more compact for $m > 2$, m being the number of observations or rows of $\underline{D}$.]

It is thus necessary to store $(\underline{D}, \underline{f})$ [or $(\underline{D}'\underline{D}, \underline{D}'\underline{f})$, which may be more compact] for possible future corrections. This can be done chronologically on tapes, however, provided that the CC keeps track of which observations are included in the current position estimate. To this end the SMSU-tape may contain the following information:

- object identification number
- $(\underline{D}'\underline{D}, \underline{D}'\underline{f})$
- time of (first, last) observation
- time of generation
- SMSU number

while the CC contains, for each star,

- object identification number
- IC data
- (C, d) or (H, h)
- list of SMSU numbers

The SMSU number is a small integer (1 or 2 bytes) which provides a compact reference to the time of observation. Now if we wish to eliminate all updates in a certain observation or generation time interval, we run through the SMSU tape searching for such updates; having found one, we look up the object in the CC and see if the SMSU number is in the list; if so, the position estimate is downdated and the SMSU number deleted from the list. At updating, we conversely add the new SMSU number to the list in CC.

This system will clearly also prevent the CC from being updated twice with the same observations, provided that the same observations are never assigned different SMSU numbers. The simplest way to prevent this is to divide the mission into fixed and uniquely defined intervals (perhaps of the order of a week), and assigning an SMSU number to each such interval.

Another important consideration is that quantities defined differentially with respect to some CC position must only be used internally to a process, which then must remember the adopted position and convert the results into "absolute" form before output. E.g. the AR will of course use the latest update (C_k, d_k) available at the time of reading the catalogue; consequently, the SM transit residuals for that star will give a correction to d_k and not to the IC position (d₀) or any other version. But at the time when the catalogue updating takes place, (C_k, d_k) is perhaps already replaced by some later version. The problem is avoided if d_k is secured by the AR programme at the same time as the current position is taken from the catalogue; when the AR later produces an observation equation

$$\underline{Dc}_k + \underline{v} = \underline{e}_k \quad (16)$$

for the correction c_k to d_k, we simply modify it by adding Dd_k on both sides:

$$\underline{D}(\underline{d}_k + \underline{c}_k) + \underline{v} = \underline{D}\underline{d}_k + \underline{e}_k \quad (17)$$

This is now an observation equation for the full difference vector w.r.t. the IC; thus the right-hand side in (11) is

$$\underline{f} = \underline{e}_k + \underline{D}\underline{d}_k \quad (18)$$

4. Process Description

4.1. Attitude Reconstitution (AR1 and AR2)

The successive steps are outlined below. Equations from Annex A of the NDAC Proposal are referenced as (A.), those from NDAC/LO/XXX as (XXX.).

- A. Define a suitable time interval for the AR. It may be of the order of a day, depending on storage and scheduling constraints. From the accuracy point of view there is probably little to gain by using intervals longer than a few hours.
- B. Define a suitable knot sequence $\{t_j\}_{j=0}^N$ for the spline representation. It should be a superset of the sequence of jet firing instants, and should satisfy $t_j - t_{j-1} \leq T_{MAX}$ for $j = 1$ to N ; $T_{MAX} \sim 100$ s (TBR).
- C. Define a reference spline $(\tilde{u}_j, \tilde{v}_j, \tilde{w}_j)$ by means of the Real-Time Attitude; see (006.3) for example.
- D. Define the *a priori* data $(\tilde{R}_1, \tilde{z}_1)$ for the first spline interval $[t_0, t_1]$. If t_0 coincides with t_N of the previous AR interval, use $(\tilde{R}_{N+1}, \tilde{z}_{N+1})$ from that; otherwise $\tilde{z}_1 = \underline{0}$ and $\tilde{R}_1$ depending on the accuracy of the RT attitude.
- E. Forward loop through the spline intervals $[t_{j-1}, t_j]$, $j = 1$ to N (filtering):
 - Ea. Compute the moments m_{jk} of the gyro signals (006.30), the reference moments $\tilde{m}_{jk}$, and the normalized observation matrix $\text{Cov}(\underline{v}_m)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (P_j, m_{jk} - \tilde{m}_{jk})$.

- Eb. For each SM transit in the spline interval, compute the reference field coordinates $(\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta})$ and σ_u from (014.7). The observations equations (006.44) are normalized and appended to the gyro observation matrix. The full observation matrix $(\underline{A}_j \underline{z}_j)$ in (A.B.4) is stored for AR2; it is recommended that also the normalization factors σ_u^{-1} are stored, so that the true transit residuals can later be recovered without recomputing the transit times. The partial derivatives $\partial u / \partial \underline{d}$ and the reference vector $\underline{d}$ are also stored for the SMSU.
- Ec. The observations $(\underline{A}_j \underline{z}_j)$ are incorporated with the predicted data $(\tilde{\underline{R}}_j \tilde{\underline{z}}_j)$ in order to get the filtered data $(\hat{\underline{R}}_j \hat{\underline{z}}_j)$ and filtered residuals $\underline{e}_j$, see (A.B.9). At this point the normalized transit residuals (last elements of $\underline{e}_j$) can be inspected and transits with large residuals given lower weight [multiplying the corresponding row of $(\underline{A}_j \underline{z}_j)$ and the normalization factor by a number < 1 ; the transformation (A.B.9) is then repeated].
- Ed. Compute the inverse transition matrix $\underline{\phi}_j^{-1}$ (note that inversion here results simply from reversing the time arrow), the process noise matrix $\underline{G}_j$ in (A.B.1) [$\equiv \text{Cov}(\underline{q}_j)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in (006.26)], and $\underline{w}_j$ in (A.B.2) [$\equiv \text{Cov}(\underline{q}_j)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \underline{E}(\underline{q}_j)$ in (006.26)]. These must be saved for the backwards recursions and also for AR2. Note however that the simple structures of $\underline{\phi}_j^{-1}$ and $\underline{G}_j$ should make it sufficient to store some 7 or 8 key numbers rather than the full matrices.
- Ee. Perform transformation (A.B.11) to get predicted data $(\tilde{\underline{R}}_j \tilde{\underline{z}}_j)$ for the next interval. Store $(\underline{U}_j, \underline{V}_j, \tilde{\underline{w}}_j)$ for the backward recursions.
- F. Loop through the spline intervals in reversed order ($j = N$ to 1) and do the smoothing recursions (A.B.14) and (optionally) the covariance recursions (A.B.18). At this point, the smoothed normalized residuals $\underline{e}_j^* = \underline{z}_j - \underline{A}_j \underline{s}_j^*$ are checked. The normalization may again be adjusted; this modification will however not be effective until AR2.

- G. Produce a preliminary attitude ephemeris based on AR2 above.
- H. Perform the IDT preprocessing for the corresponding time interval (NDAC/LO/005 and NDAC/LO/009).
- I. Perform the forward recursions of AR2 as in step E above, only with the following modifications:
- Ia. For each spline interval derive average spin rate corrections $-a^{-1}(\dot{G} - \tilde{G})(t)$ from the IDT signal phases w.r.t. the preliminary attitude. One such number is derived for each passage across the FOV of a bright enough star. Then a least-squares determination of $\underline{m}_{jk} - \tilde{\underline{m}}_{jk}$ in (006.56) gives three more "gyro" observation equations to be annexed to $(\underline{A}_j \underline{z}_j)$.
- Ib. Skip Eb and perform Ec - Ee with stored $\underline{\phi}_j^{-1}$, $\underline{G}_j$, $\underline{w}_j$.
- J. Perform the backward (smoothing) recursions as in step F. The normalized transit residuals (last elements of $\underline{e}_j^* = \underline{z}_j - \underline{A}_j \underline{s}_j^*$, with normalization factors σ_u^{-1}) are used to form right-hand sides of the SMSU observation equations (014.16). To this end they must be renormalized to the SMSU observation mean errors (σ_{SMSU}) being the sum of the transit and attitude uncertainties:
- $$\sigma_{\text{SMSU}}^2 = (\dot{u}\sigma_\tau)^2 + \underline{b}' \underline{p}_j^* \underline{b} \quad (19)$$
- where $\underline{b}'$ is the (1,3)-matrix factoring $\underline{s}_j$ in (006.44) - (006.46). The left-hand sides are formed of the partial derivatives $\partial u / \partial \underline{d}$ saved from step Eb. Finally modify the right-hand sides according to (18), using the vector $\underline{d}$ saved from step Eb.
- K. Output the final attitude and the SMSU observation matrices $(\underline{D}, \underline{f})$.

Remark: Many calculations in step Eb are common to the SM preprocessing (NDAC/LO/011) and it will clearly be useful to transfer more intermediate results than indicated in DID22.

DID 22		OUTPUT FROM : SM PREPROCESSING				PAGE : 1 OF 1					
INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION		ANNEX A		EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS	
ID	-			1. <u>For each SM transit:</u> object identification number	-	0	10 ⁸	0	1	-	8
ISM	-			Star Mapper index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
IFIELD	(-1) ^f (p8)			field index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
IGROUP	g (p14)			slit group index	-	1	2	0	1	-	1
TSTART	-			starting time (t ₀)	-	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
TAU	τ (p14)			transit time	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
SDTAU	σ _τ (p24)			estimated s.d. of TAU	s	0	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	6
ZETAA	ζ (p24)			approximate transverse field coord.	rad	-9.10 ⁻³	9.10 ⁻³	-	10 ⁻⁷	-	5
BFGD(I), I=1,3	B _{fgD} (p24)			array saved for the attitude rec.	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	-	10 ⁻⁶	6
IQUAL	-			quality index	-	-10 ⁴	10 ⁴	0	1	-	4

D I D 23	OUTPUT FROM : SM CALIBRATION INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (1)				PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 1983.01.03
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE MAX DEF MIN	NUM ACC ABS REL DIG-- ITS
ETAFG(K), K = 0 to NORD	$\eta_{fg}(\zeta)$ (p.9)	For each field index (f) and slit group index (g): polynomial coefficients, $\eta_{fg}(\zeta) = \text{ETAFG}\emptyset + \text{ETAFG1}*\text{ZETA} + \dots$	rad	-0.02 0.02 - -	10 ⁻⁹ - 8

D I D 2 4		OUTPUT FROM : GYRO DATA				PAGE : 1 OF 1		
INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (1)						DATE : 1983.01.03		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	DIG- ITS
TGYRO	-	1. <u>For each gyro frame:</u> time of first sample	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	15
NGYRO	-	number of gyros	-	0	6	0	1	1
IDGYRO(I), I = 1, NGYRO	-	gyro identification number	-	0	6	0	1	1
NSAMP	-	number of samples per gyro	-	0	10 ⁴	0	1	4
IG(ISAMP), ISAMP = 1, NSAMP	g _{ij} (p.19)	1.1. <u>For each gyro (I = 1, NGYRO):</u> gyro readings	-	0	255	0	1	3

DID 25		OUTPUT FROM : REAL TIME ATTITUDE INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (1)				PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 1983.01.03			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
IFRAME	-	1. <u>For each frame:</u> frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_k (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
RAZ	α_z (p6)	Right Ascension of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	-	12
DECZ	δ_z (p6)	Declination of z axis	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-9}	-	10
ARGZ	ω (p6)	argument of x axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	-	12
TJET	-	time of jet firing in frame	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	0	10^{-6}	-	15
THRUST(I), I = 1 to 3	$\vec{T}'JJA(\vec{T}'\vec{\omega})$ (p25)	applied thrust about $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$	Nms	-0.1	0.1	0	10^{-7}	-	6

DID 26		OUTPUT FROM : STAR CATALOGUE				PAGE : 1 OF 1					
INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (1)		ANNEX A		EXPLANATION		UNIT	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
ID	-	1. <u>For each star observed with the star mapper:</u>									
RA $\emptyset$	α_o (p4)	object identification number									
DEC $\emptyset$	δ_o (p4)	Right Ascension at TEPOCH (Input Catalogue value)									
PMRA	$\mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o$ (p4) o	Declination at TEPOCH (IC value)									
PMDEC	μ_δ (p4)	Proper Motion in R.A. at TEPOCH (times $\cos \delta_o$)									
PX	$\tilde{\omega}$ (p4)	Proper Motion in Dec. at TEPOCH									
DIFF(I), I=1,2	-	trigonometric parallax									
CDIFF(I,J) I=1,2; J=1,2	-	difference vector $\underline{d}$ w.r.t. IC									
		covariance of $\underline{d}$									
			0	10^8	0	-	1	-	8		
			$-\pi$	π	-	rad	10^{-11}	-	12		
			$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	rad	10^{-11}	-	12		
			-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	rad/s	10^{-19}	-	9		
			-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	rad/s	10^{-19}	-	9		
			$-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0	rad	10^{-11}	-	6		
			-10^{-4}	10^{-4}	0	rad	10^{-11}	-	8		
			-10^{-8}	10^{-8}	-	rad ²	10^{-15}	-	8		

DID 28		OUTPUT FROM : IDT SIGNAL CATALOGUE		PAGE : 1 OF 1			
INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (2)				DATE : 1983.01.03			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE MIN MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS
IFRAME	-	1. For each frame: frame identification number	-	1 9.10 ⁸	-	1 -	9
TMID	t _k (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0 2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶ -	15
NSTAR	-	number of objects in frame	-	0 10	0	1 -	2
ID(I)	-	1.1. For I = 1 to NSTAR: object identification number	-	0 10 ⁸	0	1 -	8
IFIELD(I)	(-1) ^f (p8)	field index	-	-1 1	0	1 -	1
ETAA(I), ZETAA(I)	$\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}$ (p32)	approximate field coordinates	rad	-9.10 ⁻³ 9.10 ⁻³	-	10 ⁻⁷ -	5
GOF(I)	-	goodness of fit	-	-10 ³⁸ 10 ³⁸	-	- 10 ⁻⁶	6
BETA(3)	$\hat{\beta}_3$ (p29)	estimated signal phase	-	-10 ³⁸ 10 ³⁸	-	- 10 ⁻⁶	6
CBETA(3,3)	$\hat{\phi}_{33}^{-1}$ (p29)	variance of BETA(3)	-	-10 ³⁸ 10 ³⁸	-	- 10 ⁻⁶	6

DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE		DEF	NUM ACC		DIG-ITS
				MIN	MAX		ABS	REL	
DID 29	OUTPUT FROM : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (1) INPUT TO : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (2)							PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 1983.01.03	
NKNOT	N (p47)	1. For each AR interval: number of knots (spline intervals)	-	0	10^4	0	1	-	4
TKNOT	t_j (p47)	1.1. For each spline interval: time of knot	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
ARRAY1(I), I=1,10	-	values defining ϕ_j^{-1} and G_j	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
WMEAN(I), I=1,16	$\bar{w}_j$ (p47)	mean of process noise vector	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
AZJ(K,I), K=1,3n; I=1,16	$(A_j z_j)$ (p48)	normalized observation equations for n gyros, n = 3 presumably	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
NSMT	-	number of SM transits	-	0	99	-	1	-	2
AZJ1(I), I=1,16	$(A_j z_j)$	1.1.1. For each SM transit: normalized observation equation	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
ZNORM	-	normalization factor σ_u^{-1}	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
DIFF(I), I=1,2	-	difference vector $\underline{d}$ w.r.t. IC	rad	-10^{-4}	10^{-4}	0	10^{-11}	-	8
ARRAY2(I), I=1,6?	-	other data: $\underline{u}_T, \underline{b}, \partial u / \partial \underline{d}$, etc	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6

DID 2		OUTPUT FROM : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION				PAGE : 1 OF 1	
INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION						DATE : 82.05.05	
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE MAX MIN	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	DIG- ITS REL
IFRAME	-	1. <u>For each frame:</u> frame identification number	-	9.10 ⁸ 1	-	1	9
TMID	t _κ (p31)	frame mid-time	s	2.10 ⁸ 0	-	10 ⁻⁶	15
RAZ	α _z (p6)	Right Ascension of z axis	rad	π -π	-	10 ⁻¹¹	12
DECZ	δ _z (p6)	Declination of z axis	rad	½π -½π	-	10 ⁻⁹	10
ARGZ	ω (p6)	argument of x axis	rad	π -π	-	10 ⁻¹¹	12

DID 12		OUTPUT FROM : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION INPUT TO : IDT PREPROCESSING				PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.09.15		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	DIG- ITS
IFRAME	-	1. <u>For each frame:</u> frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	9
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	15
RAZ	α_z (p6)	Right Ascension of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	12
DECZ	δ_z (p6)	Declination of z axis	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-9}	10
ARGZ	ω (p6)	argument of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	12
KFIRST, KLAST	-	if an attitude discontinuity has occurred in the frame, these give the first and last sample affected	-	0	9000	0	1	4

DID 30	OUTPUT FROM : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION (2)		PAGE : 1 OF 1						
	INPUT TO : STAR MAPPER STARS UPDATE		DATE : 1983.01.03						
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
ISMSU	-	1. <u>For each SMSU interval:</u> SMSU number	-	0	255	0	1	-	3
TBEG, TEND	-	interval limits (from TSTART)	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	0	10^{-6}	-	15
ID	-	1.1. <u>For each star observed in</u> <u>the SMSU interval:</u> object identification number	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8
TOBS0, TOBS1	-	time of first and last observation	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	0	10^{-6}	-	15
TGEN	-	time of generation	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	0	10^{-6}	-	15
DDDF(I,J), I=1,2; J=1,3	-	normal equations matrix (<u>D'D</u> <u>D'f</u>)	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	0	-	10^{-15}	15

DID 31	OUTPUT FROM : STAR CATALOGUE INPUT TO : STAR MAPPER STARS UPDATE					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 1983.01.03		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE MIN MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS	
ID HH(I,J), I=1,2; J=I,3 NSMSU LSMSU(K), K=1,NSMSU	- - - -	1. <u>For each star observed with the star mapper:</u> object identification number information array (<u>H</u> <u>h</u>) or (<u>C</u> <u>d</u>) for current position estimate number of updatings list of SMSU numbers	- - - -	0 10 ⁸ -10 ³⁸ 10 ³⁸ 0 99 0 255	0 - - -	1 - - 10 ⁻¹⁵ 1 - 1 -	8 15 2 3	

DID 32		OUTPUT FROM : STAR MAPPER STARS UPDATE				PAGE : 1 OF 1		
INPUT TO : STAR CATALOGUE						DATE : 1983.01.03		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS
ID	-	1. <u>For each star observed with the star mapper:</u> object identification number	-	0	10 ⁸	-	1 -	8
HH(I,J), I=1,2; J=I,3	-	information array (<u>H</u> <u>h</u>) or (<u>C</u> <u>d</u>) for current position estimate	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	- 10 ⁻¹⁵	15
NSMSU	-	number of updatings	-	0	99	-	1 -	2
LSMSU(K), K=1, NSMSU	-	list of SMSU numbers	-	0	255	-	1 -	3

NDAC PROCESS DIAGRAM (82.12.28) 24(24)

